

Effects of Dithering on Co-Added 5σ Depth in Cronos.92 Run of the Operations Simulator

K. Simon Krughoff
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Abstract

Using a simple dithering pattern based on a triangular tessellation of the inscribed hexagon, we show that the co-added 5σ depth is significantly increased relative to the non-dithered cadence. We show that the distribution of depth values is also much smoother, and well behaved in the dithered case. The results for the g and r filters are presented here. The other filters will be shown in an addendum.

1 Introduction

With static pointings, there is significant spacial variation in depth in the Cronos.92 run of the Operations Simulator (OpSim). Due to overlap between adjacent circular apertures, the lenticular intersection regions are visited \sim two times more than the non-overlapping sections of the field. While this is beneficial for programs requiring maximal depth, it is detrimental to most other programs which benefit from a smooth selection function.

In order to address the question of whether a simple dithering scheme can provide a flatter two dimensional depth field, we have employed a vertex walk style dithering which will offset the original field centers on a night by night basis. We then pixelized a section of the survey with Ryan Scranton's SDSSPix method. Histograms of the co-added 5σ depth were produced as the figure of merit for the dithering scheme.

§2 describes the dithering scheme. §3 describes the pixelization scheme. §4 describes the selection of pointings used in the construction of the figures of merit. In §5 we present our findings. §6 includes discussion and conclusions.

2 A Vertex Walk Dithering Scheme

The primary question involved in constructing a dithering scheme is how to construct it without undoing all the beneficial parts of the survey construction. In our case, we need to preserve the visit pairs intended to facilitate detection of the near Earth objects. These pairs are done on a nightly basis, so the offset must be constant on timescales of a day.

The offsets are calculated from the vertexes of the triangular tessellation of hexagon inscribed in the instrument footprint. The tessellation should be coarse enough that there is a high probability of walking the entire grid by the end of the survey. With the definition that the number of rows of vertexes, $nrows = 2^{level} + 1$, a level of 4 implies 17 rows. Assuming equilateral triangles, this gives a total of 217 nodes. Figure 1 shows how the grid is traversed, starting at the lower-leftmost vertex and proceeding along the solid line to the upper-right.

Offsets for a particular night are calculated as follows:

- Retrieve night number indexed from the first night of the survey.
- Calculate vertex number indexed from the south-western most vertex progressing along the solid line in Figure 1 by:
 $vertex_id = night_id \% number_of_nodes + 1$.
- Apply offsets to field centers in Cronos.92 visited on that night.

2.1 Distribution of Offsets

3 SDSSPix

In order to calculate the distribution of co-added depths from the Cronos.92 run, it was necessary to pixelize the survey pointings in a way that would allow the use of the pointing metadata for calculating the 5σ depth. We employed the SDSSPix routines (R. Scranton, PITT) to pixelize the individual pointings. We then refined all pixels to the finest mesh and calculated co-added 5σ limiting magnitude for common pixels.

4 Sample Selection

Since the pixelization is both computationally and storage space intensive, we chose a sub section of the Cronos.92 run of the OpSim to pixelize. We required that the field centers be in the bounds $180^\circ < RA < 250^\circ$ and $-30^\circ < Declination < 10^\circ$. Once a common resolution pixelization was reached, the pointings covering each pixel were used to calculate the co-added 5σ limiting magnitude at the location of the pixel in question for a particular filter. A further cut on the included fields was done to require that only the fields observed for the Universal Cadence proposal (PropID = 259) be used. This was done in two parts. First an effective exposure time was calculated from the simulated 5σ limiting magnitude for each individual observation, then the co-added 5σ limiting magnitude was calculated from the total effective exposure time.

$$t_{eff} = \sum_i 10^{(m_{5i}-25.0)/1.25} \quad (1)$$

$$m_{5coadded} = 1.25 \times \log_{10}(t_{eff}) + 25.0 \quad (2)$$

where t_{eff} is the total effective exposure time for all i observations, m_{5i} is the 5σ limiting magnitude for the i^{th} exposure, and $m_{5coadded}$ is the co-added 5σ limiting magnitude.

Once the co-added 5σ limiting magnitudes were calculated for each pixel, a cut was done in RA and Dec to remove edge effects. Figure 2 shows the result for the original, non-dithered section of Cronos.92 in the SDSS-r filter. Figure 3 shows how the depth changes when our dithering scheme is applied. Figures 4 & 5 show the same thing for the SDSS-g band.

5 5σ Limiting Magnitude Distribution

Once the pixelized map of co-added 5σ limiting magnitudes is calculated, one can do any number of calculations on the resulting scalar field. We choose as our figure of merit the histogram of co-added limiting magnitude. For both the g and r, bands we use bins of 0.01 in magnitude. Figure 6 (left) shows that in the SDSS-r band, the distribution of co-added 5σ limiting magnitudes reduces from an obviously bimodal distribution to a much smoother single peaked shape. This suggests that the depth is varying much more smoothly as a function of position in the dithered case. Figure 6 (right) shows the same set of histograms for the SDSS-g band. In the g band, the distribution collapses from bimodal to an almost perfect Gaussian. We can fit Gaussian models to each of the cases to get a handle on how the two cases address the requirements in the LSST SRD. For the non-dithered case, we fit a sum of two Gaussians model. For the dithered case, a single Gaussian is sufficient to model the distribution. Table 1 lists the results of the Gaussian model fits and how they compare to the values in the SRD.

Name	σ_1	$\langle \rangle_1$	σ_2	$\langle \rangle_2$	SRD value
Non-Dithered r	0.0767	27.41	0.0928	27.81	27.5
Dithered r	0.1002	27.53	N/A	N/A	27.5
Non-Dithered g	0.0843	27.30	0.07197	27.69	27.4
Dithered g	0.1104	27.41	N/A	N/A	27.4

Table 1: Fit parameters for Gaussian models

6 Discussion

The application of a dithering scheme, even the simple one described here, succeeds in significantly smoothing the variation of co-added depth as a function of position. We have shown that the dithering scheme does not fail for either the g or r bands in the Cronos.92 run. Furthermore, the dithering scheme reproduces the requirement presented in the LSST SRD for both the g and r bands.

Figure 1: The dithering scheme walks the vertexes of a triangular tessellation of the hexagon inscribed in the circular approximation of the instrument footprint. The solid line shows the progression from the lower left to the upper right.

Figure 2: Subsection of the Cronos.92 run (PropID = 259) in the r band without dithering.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 2 with dithering turned on.

Figure 4: Subsection of the Cronos.92 run (PropID = 259) in the g band without dithering.

Figure 5: Same as Figure 4 with dithering turned on.

Figure 6: Histogram of $m_{5\text{coadded}}$ for the r (left) and g (right) bands. In both panes the dashed green line is for the dithered case and the solid red line is for the non-dithered case.